

PINNED FOAM CORE SANDWICH FOR IMPROVED DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF RACING YACHTS

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SUMMARY

The resistance of racing yachts to slamming loads is one of the factors limiting their performance, but data on sandwich damage tolerance, even qualitative data, is rarely available. A special test has therefore been developed, in order to evaluate alternatives to the honeycomb sandwich currently widely used. Test results show that pinned foam core can provide a three-fold improvement in damage tolerance compared to honeycomb for the same areal weight; numerical modeling has been used to understand the structural response.

Keywords: Sandwich, Impact, 3-D reinforcement, Micro-tomography, FE model

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are extensively used in multihull racing yacht construction such as the trimaran shown in Figure 1, mainly carbon/epoxy prepreg. This may either be in monolithic form, for certain hull areas or appendices for example, or as a thin skin on honeycomb or foam sandwich in the hull and mast structures.

Figure 1. *Groupama 3* racing multi-hull

These are very large composite structures, the central hull of the *Groupama 3* trimaran is 31.5 meters long, Figure 2.

Figure 2. Central hull assembly.

Weight gain is essential and architects and designers perform detailed analyses to optimise stiffness and strength [1]. However, most of these are quasi-static, with empirical coefficients to account for dynamic effects. Impact loading of boat hulls by waves is complex and “slamming” and wave impact, which involve a localized pressure pulse travelling over a limited area of the hull, have been described by several authors [2-4]. These can seriously damage sandwich structures, and are usually taken into account in design as an equivalent pressure [5]. However, there is considerable uncertainty over the safety factors required for this loading despite several measurement campaigns for different vessels (e.g. [6-8]). The slamming pulse is very short, typically lasting tens of milli-seconds, so special equipment is needed to record it and to correlate the recording with navigation conditions.

In order to improve the damage tolerance of racing yachts it is essential to have a test which applies loads which are representative of those seen in service. Most impact studies are performed using rigid impacters. While these may be of interest for floating body impacts they do not produce the same type of damage in sandwich materials as that observed after repeated wave impact. A few studies in which boats or sections of boats have been dropped into water are available but these tests are very expensive, and not suited to material comparisons [9-11]. A recent paper describes a test set-up specifically designed to examine controlled velocity impacts of panels on water, but this requires a complex dedicated test machine [12].

This paper presents results from a study to characterize the behaviour of sandwich panels subjected to “deformable body” impacts. A test method has been developed to simulate the wave loading of boat hull structures, based on dropping flexible medicine balls of different weights from increasing heights onto rigidly fixed panels. The test principle was described at a previous ICCM conference [13]. However, since then the test has been modified and improved considerably, and extensive instrumentation has been added in order to provide data for correlation with modelling. There have also been significant material developments since the previous paper, with the appearance of pinned foam sandwich materials [14-17], Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of pinned foam sandwich.

These offer many possibilities for tailoring properties but little is known of their impact response and even less of their behaviour when subjected to wave impacts. The aim of the present work is to compare the response of a particular pinned foam sandwich material with that of the honeycomb core sandwich, of the same weight currently used in multi-hull yacht construction, loaded under identical conditions.

MATERIALS

The “medicine ball” test has been applied to a wide range of materials in recent years, from monolithic and stiffened monolithic panels to foam (polymer and aluminium) and honeycomb core sandwich of different densities. Here results from two materials are discussed:

- Nomex honeycomb cores. The basic core density which will be discussed here is 64 kg/m^3 , with hexagonal 5mm cells, but other densities and forms were tested in the preliminary study to examine the influence of these parameters. Two forms of cell were examined, OX (over expanded) in the preliminary study, and hexagonal for the tests described here.

- Pinned foam, the same polyimide foam reinforced in the through-thickness direction with pultruded carbon fibre reinforced pins of 0.51mm diameter in four directions at $\pm 30^\circ$ to the facings (Figures 3 and 4). This resulted in an equivalent overall density to that of the honeycomb core panel, 64 kg/ m^3 .

Figure 4. Fracture surfaces from out-of-plane tensile tests on pinned foam core (left) and 5mm honeycomb (right).

TEST METHOD

Figure 5 shows the current set-up, with one of the medicine balls placed at the centre of a metre square sandwich panel. The latter is rigidly fixed inside a steel frame.

Figure 5. Impacter ball on sandwich panel

Medicine balls with the same envelope but weighted differently (up to 40 kg) are dropped from increasing heights, up to 6 meters. The panel is inspected after each impact and data are analysed; when damage is detected the panel is removed and sectioned. Extensive instrumentation is used, both to characterize the panel response and to provide data to correlate with numerical models. This includes measurement of:

- force during the impact (four load cells at each corner of the panel),
- central panel displacement (laser transducer),
- panel strains (three strain gauges),
- steel frame displacement (second laser transducer),
- impactor shape changes (high speed camera),
- pressure distribution (pressure sensitive paper).

More test details can be found elsewhere [18].

RESULTS

Tests performed

Table 1 summarizes the test sequences for each material up to failure.

Table 1. Impact test sequences

Material	Honeycomb	Pinned foam
Impact energy, Joules	184 (x3) 369 553	184 (x3) 369 553 737 922 1106 1292

Instrumentation

These tests produce a large amount of data. The limited space available here does not allow a complete presentation, one example of load and central displacement data is shown in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Example of force and central displacement data recorded, lowest impact energy, pinned foam sandwich.

Loads close to one ton are measured during even the lowest energy impact. The impact duration is less than 30 ms. More details of data and results from tests to show the reproducibility and repeatability of the test are given in [18].

Damage

The results for the two types of panel (honeycomb and pinned foam) are very different. At 553 J the honeycomb core shows an extensive crushed zone. The honeycomb buckles, resulting in permanent damage and a loss of panel properties. For the pinned foam sandwich panel no damage was detected at this height, and tests continued up to a 1292 J impact energy before any damage was detected. This indicates the excellent potential of this pinned foam sandwich for areas of boat structures where impact performance is critical.

After testing sections of the panel were removed and an X-ray micro-tomography study was performed [19] to examine the damage mechanisms in the two materials. Figure 7 shows two examples of the results, for samples subjected to through-thickness compression tests.

Figure 7. X-ray micro-tomography images of damage in a) honeycomb and b) pinned foam cores after compression tests.

This is a very powerful technique, which enables 3-D images of the internal sandwich structure to be obtained without cutting the samples. Cell wall buckling in the honeycomb core is clearly seen. For the pinned foam the only damage noted is a debonding of some pins from the facing (upper right photo in Figure 6b).

FE Modelling

In order to analyse the panel response to this type of impact, dynamic numerical modelling has been performed, using the finite element method with implicit time integration. This gives access to the medicine ball deformations during impact and to the variations of the pressure field during impact in both temporal and spatial fields. Figure 8 shows one of the numerical models developed, using the ADINA version 8.5.0 finite element software. Due to structure symmetries, only one quarter of the ball and panel is meshed.

It is important to model the medicine ball correctly: The envelope of the ball is modelled using quadratic shell elements with an isotropic linear elastic material model, the sand in the ball using quadratic three-dimensional elements with a non-linear Mohr-Coulomb material model. High speed camera images enabled the deformed ball shape to be compared to model predictions.

For the sandwich panel, the skins are modelled using quadratic multi-layered shell elements with an orthotropic linear elastic material model. The cores are represented using quadratic three-dimensional elements with an orthotropic linear elastic material model for the honeycomb. The contact between the panel and the ball is assumed to be frictionless, and is controlled by a constraint function method [20]. The sandwich panel is perfectly clamped on its edges. A very small structural damping is introduced using Rayleigh factors to stabilize the vibrations.

Figure 8. FE mesh just before impact (upper) and at maximum displacement (lower) for a 184J impact on honeycomb sandwich panel

Figure 9 shows one example of results from modelling and test for the same impact. The predicted central panel displacement is slightly lower than the measured value. The model is very useful for parametric studies, for example on Figure 9 the results from simulations of the impact on panels with different transverse shear modulus values are shown. It is apparent that it would require a very large change in shear modulus compared to the manufacturer's value (a reduction of over 50%) to adjust the model to the test results. Similar studies varying other parameters (geometry, facing properties,

impacter behaviour) and comparison with results from tests on a range of materials are being used to understand how energy is absorbed during impact and how damage tolerance can be improved.

Figure 9. Example of results, for honeycomb sandwich.

CONCLUSIONS

An instrumented medicine ball test has been developed and employed to evaluate the damage resistance of pinned foam core sandwich materials. These are shown to offer great potential to improve the damage tolerance of composite multi-hull yacht structures compared to the currently-used honeycomb sandwich materials. Pinned foam sandwich is a new type of material, and optimisation of pin type, spacing and orientation offers a multitude of possibilities. Modelling is essential if best use is to be made of these materials and first results from a numerical study are presented here.

Both modelling and experimental studies of these and alternative materials (foam core, metallic honeycomb, monolithic and stiffened structures) are continuing.

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